

IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND METHODS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES

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Abstract. Language learning is not limited to the knowledge of the structure, but also to its function. Incorporating various approaches and methods into ESP teaching has become a crucial criterion in syllabus creation. Implementation of these special methods and approaches promotes qualitative lesson plans and thus makes students feel engaged in various task completion such as advanced reading comprehension. Composing a speech for a presentation on a particular topic, essay writing, round-table discussions and a number of other assignments. This article is devoted to discussion of some methods and approaches of teaching ESP in particular for students of international relations and political science.

Key words: Communicative language teaching (CLT), Task-based language teaching (TBLT), Content and language integrated learning (CLIL), ESP, approach, method, communication

Introduction

The inception of ESP teaching dates back to its implementation at the workplaces for staff development. Since the 1980s, there has been significant progress in the field of ESP, as learners' needs altered along with advancements in technology. It has been suggested that ESP lacks a definitive method. However in

reality there are numerous methods and approaches that can be effectively employed by teachers based on the level of students and the field they are studying in. For instance, when working with a group of graduate political scientists seeking to enhance their communication skills what method would be most appropriate? Options such as CLT, TBLT or CLIL could be considered. As soon as teachers evaluate specific needs of their students, the curriculum can be tailored accordingly. For educators, whether as for teachers, lecturers, or instructors, the choice of approach or method that best aligns with the needs of his or her learners plays a crucial role. In the context of ESP, a notable advantage is that participants tend to be more motivated and receptive to the knowledge imparted by the instructor.

Communicative language teaching (CLT)

This approach is considered to be one of the most popular models for teaching ESP. CLT approach aims to put students in a variety of real-life situations. Thus, they develop their language skills and learn how to communicate in the real world. Teachers' objective in this process is to focus on fluency of communication rather than accuracy.

CLT is distinguished by engaging and relevant classroom activities, accompanied by authentic source materials. Students are provided with as much opportunity to share and get meaningful communication as possible.

A wide range of approaches and methods have been developed worldwide for language teaching over the years.

Savignon (1997) defined communicative competence as the expression, interpretation, and negotiation of meaning; and CLT encourages language learners to acquire language knowledge as well as the ability to use the language. Unlike the traditional teaching approaches, CLT is rooted in a shift “from emphasis on form to emphasis on communication” (Cook, 2003, p. 36). It also involves classroom activities that engage learners with language use in a more meaningful and authentic

manner. CLT thereby supports the teaching and learning processes by enhancing their power and vitality.

CLT enables language learners to communicate in target language. That is, learning takes place “through the process of struggling to communicate” (Finocchiaro & Brumfit, in Brown, 2007, p. 49). Teaching methods and approaches vary depending on teaching-related aspects and factors; such as motivation, classroom interaction, and classroom setting. These approaches include grammar translation, audio-lingual, and communicative language teaching (CLT) approaches. It is the researcher’s view; however, that whenever a teaching or learning approach or method focuses on a specific aspect at the expense of others, an area of imperfection results. The study critically assessed certain issues related to CLT and examined the implications of method for teaching and learning. The study has also provided opinions and evidence, while referring to the arguments and ideas presented in the CLT literature. The teacher’s role is to facilitate, advise, and guide the learners in the classroom; while the language learners are communicators, who negotiate the meanings that are unclear. CLT concentrates on one strong aspect of teaching and considers it as the source of learning-communication.

According to Wafaa Abdullah Alamri (2018) CLT encourages language learners to acquire language knowledge as well as the ability to use the language. Unlike the traditional teaching approaches, CLT is rooted in a shift “from emphasis on form to emphasis on communication” Wafaa Abdullah Alamri (2018) states that due to CLT students can be involved in communication through target language. She mentions that the teacher’s role is to alleviate, consult, and guide the learners in the classroom; while the language learners are communicators, who negotiate the meanings that are unclear.

As an example, for students of political science and international relations CLT approach can be implemented in the form of public speech activity: students perform on behalf of famous politicians showing their oratory skills in front of groupmates.

Task-based language teaching (TBLT)

TBLT language teaching is directed on a detailed task completion which engages and grabs attention of the learners. TBLT approach is divided into three distinct phases – a pre-task, the task itself and post-task review.

For example, students of political science and international may prepare a presentation about Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as poverty reduction, quality education, good health and well-being and so on established by the United Nations (UN). To complete this task, students need to be engaged in all three phases: they should listen or read the source material and write notes at a pre-task phase, which is followed by carrying out internet research as well. The pre-task stage can also often include playing a recording of people doing the task. Speaking in the form of presentation can be a part of the second phase- a task itself. The discussion of feedbacks given by groupmates or a teacher may be a constituent of a post-task review.

Swan (2005) emphasizes the main characteristics of TBLT:

- Instructed language acquisition should primarily focus on the use of natural or naturalistic language, with activities emphasizing meaning over linguistic form.

- Instruction should prioritize learner-centered approaches over teacher-centered methods.

- Engaging in more formal language study, either prior to or following a task, could prove advantageous. This approach may enhance internalization by fostering or optimizing familiarity with formal characteristics in communication.

- Conventional methods tend to be ineffective and inappropriate, especially when they necessitate passive formal teaching and practice that is disconnected from interactive engagement.

Anne Dorathy and Dr. S.N. Mahalakshmi (2016) highlight the advantages of Task Based Language Teaching:

-Task-based learning effectively shifts the emphasis of the educational process from the instructor to the learner.

-It provides the student with an alternative perspective on language, viewing it as a means rather than merely an end.

-It has the potential to transform instruction from theoretical concepts to practical implementation in real-world scenarios.

-A task serves to effectively address the immediate needs of learners while offering a structured framework for designing engaging classes that cater to the requirements of students.

Content and language integrated learning (CLIL)

As Nam Phuong Le and Phoebe Nguyen (2022) claim that CLIL is a combination of the language and content directed on developing the learners' language skills and specific knowledge at the same time. In other words [the CLIL approach](#) means an integration of studying one subject (for example, diplomacy, economy, history or political science) together with learning a language, for instance English.

The organization of language teaching is dependent on demands of the first subject rather than the language itself.

The language teaching is organized around the demands of the first subject rather than that of the target language. It is essential to ensure that the integration is transparent and that students are actively involved. Nevertheless, the CLIL approach presents considerable opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration; it broadens the scope of language learning and can effectively re-engage students who may have previously lost motivation.

Nam Phuong Le and Phoebe Nguyen (2022) distinguish a 4Cs framework which includes the gist of the CLIL method:

1. Content
2. Cognition

3. Communication

4. Culture.

First stage(content) assumes that students get acquainted with the content from the language lesson. At the second stage(cognition) of CLIL students develop their cognition skills by creating their own content version which needs to be analyzed for its linguistic demands. Third stage(communication) is about learning the language in a different context. Finally, at the stage of culture, students develop a critical component to draw upon a foreign language.

With regard to students of political science and international relations, CLIL approach can be used while teaching topical vocabulary, organizing MUN conference among students or even debates.

Conclusion

Having explored several methods and approaches for ESP teaching, I can assume that there is no specific or universal one. In ESP teachers need to implement them in accordance with types of learner, demand, expectations, time, abilities of learners and context it will be presented in.

The main advantage of investigated approaches and methods is students' involvement not only into the process of language learning but into other subject knowledge at the same time. It is worth noticing again methods such as **Communicative language teaching (CLT)** and **Task-based language teaching (TBLT)**. They significantly enhance teachers' skills of conducting lessons and raise students' motivation.

However, from my perspective, among all approaches mentioned in this article I want to point **Content and language integrated learning (CLIL)** as owing to CLIL students have opportunity to learn language in a more natural way. As it was mentioned before CLIL includes four competencies; content, cognition, communication, and culture which provide more profound foreign language acquisition.

REFERENCES:

1. Wafaa Abdullah Alamri (2018). Communicative Language Teaching: Possible Alternative Approaches to CLT and Teaching Contexts: *English Language Teaching*; Vol. 11, No. 10; 2018 doi: 10.5539/elt.v11n10p132; URL: <http://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v11n10p132>
2. Swan, M. (2005). Legislation by Hypothesis: The Case of Task-Based Instruction. *Applied Linguistics* 26 (3), 376–401
3. Anne Dorathy and Dr. S.N. Mahalakshmi (2016). Task-Based Language Teaching - A Powerful Approach for Maximizing Learning and Teaching in L2 Acquisition: *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*; Vol. 6, No. 7, July 2016, pp. 1822-1832. DOI: 10.5958/2249-7315.2016.00546.3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304781125_Task-Based_Language_Teaching_-_A_Powerful_Approach_for_Maximizing_Learning_and_Teaching_in_L2_Acquisition
4. As Nam Phuong Le and Phoebe Nguyen (2022). Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) Method and How It Is Changing the Foreign Language Learning Landscape: *Open Access Library Journal*; Volume 9, e8381 ISSN Online: 2333-9721 ISSN Print: 2333-9705. DOI: 10.4236/oalib.1108381. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358514442_Content_and_Language_Integrated_Learning_CLIL_Method_and_How_It_Is_Changing_the_Foreign_Language_Learning_Landscape.